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GLACIOLOGY AND HAS NOT BEEN PEER-REVIEWED.

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Journal:	<i>Journal of Glaciology</i>
Manuscript ID	JOG-2026-0027
Manuscript Type:	Letter
Date Submitted by the Author:	27-Feb-2026
Complete List of Authors:	Greve, Ralf; Hokkaido University, Institute of Low Temperature Science Staroszczyk, Ryszard; Institute of Hydroengineering,
Keywords:	Glacier flow, Ice dynamics, Ice temperature, Ice-sheet modelling
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The Smith–Morland flow law revisited

Ralf GREVE^{1,2}, Ryszard STAROSZCZYK³

¹*Institute of Low Temperature Science, Hokkaido University, Sapporo, Japan*

²*Arctic Research Center, Hokkaido University, Sapporo, Japan*

³*Institute of Hydro-Engineering, Polish Academy of Sciences, Kościerska 7, 80-328 Gdańsk, Poland*

Correspondence: Ryszard Staroszczyk <rstar@ibwpan.gda.pl>

ABSTRACT. The standard Nye–Glen flow law for ice deformation contains a physically questionable infinite-viscosity singularity at zero stress. We revisit the polynomial Smith–Morland flow law as a singularity-free alternative. After rescaling the law into a modern non-dimensional framework, we find that the original parameters produce ice that is significantly too soft. Using an idealized EISMINT Phase 2 steady-state test, we recalibrate the law to match the ice volume of the standard Nye–Glen law, resulting in a slow-down factor of 5.776. Validation via a steady-state Greenland ice-sheet simulation shows that the modified law produces realistic geometries and velocities. Notably, the Smith–Morland law’s linear term leads to faster flow in low-stress regions and favours thermomechanical fingering instabilities in the ice-sheet interior. The results demonstrate that the modified Smith–Morland law is a viable, physically consistent alternative for large-scale ice-flow modelling.

1 INTRODUCTION

The total flow velocity of an ice sheet or glacier is the sum of two primary components: internal deformation and basal sliding. The relative contribution of each process varies strongly depending on the temperature of the ice and the condition of the bed. While internal deformation is always present, even if the ice is frozen to its bed, basal sliding tends to be the dominant component for temperate-based glaciers and especially fast-flowing ice streams.

26 Internal deformation, the focus of this study, results from the viscous creep of polycrystalline ice with
27 a homologous temperature (ratio between the absolute temperature and the pressure melting point) close
28 to unity. This process is often described by the Nye–Glen flow law, which treats ice as a purely viscous,
29 incompressible, non-Newtonian fluid, and assumes a power-law relation between the strain rate and the
30 stress (Glen, 1955; Nye, 1957). It has two parameters, the stress exponent n and the rate factor A , which
31 depends strongly on temperature. The value of the stress exponent is often chosen as $n = 3$. However,
32 this has been a matter of debate: a range from 1.5 to 4.2 has been considered (Cuffey and Paterson, 2010),
33 some recent ice-sheet-modelling studies discussed $n = 4$ (Bons and others, 2018; Millstein and others, 2022;
34 Getraer and Morlighem, 2025), and for temperate ice, recent evidence from laboratory experiments even
35 suggests $n = 1$ (Schohn and others, 2025).

36 For any $n > 1$, the Nye–Glen flow law produces an infinite-viscosity limit for zero stress or strain rate.
37 This singularity is both physically doubtful and numerically problematic. Regularization can be achieved
38 by adding a constant residual stress to the nonlinear power law (Greve and Blatter, 2009), or by defining
39 a small positive minimum value for either the stress, the strain rate or the fluidity (inverse viscosity).

40 A polynomial flow law, which does not feature the singularity due to the presence of a linear term, was
41 proposed by Smith and Morland (1981), constrained by laboratory data from various sources (Steinemann,
42 1954; Glen, 1955; Steinemann, 1958; Mellor and Testa, 1969b,a). These data feature a substantial spread,
43 which leads to a significant uncertainty in the parameters of the Smith–Morland flow law. It has been used
44 in several follow-up studies (Morland, 1984, 1997, 2001; Cliffe and Morland, 2000, 2001, 2002; Morland and
45 Staroszczyk, 2003, 2006, 2019, 2020); however, it has not seen widespread consideration, and it has never
46 (to the best of our knowledge) been applied to a real-world problem. Nevertheless, we consider the Smith–
47 Morland flow law an interesting alternative to the Nye–Glen flow law that is worth further investigation.
48 In this study, we first rescale the Smith–Morland flow law such that it agrees with the non-dimensional
49 framework by Greve (2025). We then argue that the flow law is distinctly too “fast” (that is, the ice
50 exhibits excessive fluidity) and produces unrealistically large flow velocities. Therefore, we recalibrate the
51 flow law by running tests with the ice-sheet model SICOPOLIS (SIMulation COde for POLythermal Ice
52 Sheets; SICOPOLIS Authors, 2025). We consider experiment A from the suite of the EISMINT (European
53 Ice Sheet Modelling INiTiative) Phase 2 Simplified Geometry Experiments (Payne and others, 2000) and
54 iteratively adjust the coefficients of the Smith–Morland flow law such that the resulting steady-state ice
55 volume matches the one obtained with the Nye–Glen flow law. As a consequence, the resulting “modified

56 Smith–Morland flow law” produces strain rates overall comparable to those obtained with the Nye–Glen
57 flow law.

58 As a real-world application, we consider a simple steady-state scenario for the Greenland ice sheet. The
59 results confirm that the surface velocities obtained with the Nye–Glen flow law and the modified Smith–
60 Morland flow law are similar to each other (and observations), while those obtained with the original
61 (rescaled) Smith–Morland flow law are excessive.

62 2 SMITH–MORLAND FLOW LAW

63 2.1 Original form

The flow law formulated by Smith and Morland (1981) is a collinear relation between the strain-rate (stretching) tensor d_{ij} and the stress deviator (traceless part of the full stress tensor) t_{ij}^D :

$$\frac{d_{ij}}{[d]_{\text{SM}}} = \tilde{A}(\tilde{T}) \left[c_{0,\text{SM}} + c_{1,\text{SM}} \left(\frac{\tau_e}{[\tau]_{\text{SM}}} \right)^2 + c_{2,\text{SM}} \left(\frac{\tau_e}{[\tau]_{\text{SM}}} \right)^4 \right] \frac{t_{ij}^D}{[\tau]_{\text{SM}}}, \quad (1)$$

here formulated in Cartesian index notation with indices $i, j = 1, 2, 3$, corresponding to the spatial directions x, y, z . The quantity τ_e is the effective stress, defined as $\tau_e = [(t_{ij}^D t_{ij}^D)/2]^{1/2}$ (summation over both i and j implied). In contrast to Nye–Glen-type power laws (Glen, 1955; Nye, 1957), this flow law depends on the effective stress via a three-term polynomial, including an absolute term that prevents the infinite-viscosity limit when the effective stress approaches zero. The scales (typical values) are chosen as

$$[\tau]_{\text{SM}} = 5 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa} \quad (\text{typical deviatoric stress}), \quad (2a)$$

$$[d]_{\text{SM}} = 200 \text{ a}^{-1} \quad (\text{typical strain rate}), \quad (2b)$$

and the dimensionless coefficients have the values

$$c_{0,\text{SM}} = 8.34 \times 10^{-3}, \quad c_{1,\text{SM}} = 0.200, \quad c_{2,\text{SM}} = 0.463 \quad (3)$$

(Smith and Morland, 1981, Eq. (29a)). The dimensionless rate factor $\tilde{A}(\tilde{T})$ depends on the temperature relative to the pressure melting point, T' (Smith and Morland, 1981, Eq. (14) and accompanying text), via

the two-term exponential function

$$\tilde{A}(\tilde{T}) = 0.7242 \exp(11.9567 \tilde{T}) + 0.3438 \exp(2.9494 \tilde{T}), \quad \tilde{T} = \frac{T' - T_0}{[\Delta T]}, \quad (4)$$

64 where \tilde{T} is the dimensionless temperature relative to the pressure melting point, $T_0 = 273.15$ K and
 65 $[\Delta T] = 20$ K (Smith and Morland, 1981, Eq. (21c)). For temperatures near the pressure melting point,
 66 this expression yields values of order unity.

67 2.2 Rescaled flow law

The scales (2) introduced by Smith and Morland (1981) are both unrealistically large for flow situations that occur in natural ice sheets or glaciers. Therefore, in several follow-up studies in which the Smith–Morland flow law was used (Morland, 1984, 1997, 2001; Cliffe and Morland, 2000, 2001, 2002; Morland and Staroszczyk, 2003, 2006, 2019, 2020), smaller values for the scales of the deviatoric stress, $[\tau]$, and the strain rate, $[d]$, were chosen. We specify them as

$$[\tau]_{\text{SM}} = \alpha [\tau], \quad (5a)$$

$$[d]_{\text{SM}} = \beta [d], \quad (5b)$$

where the rescaling factors α and β are both assumed to be greater than unity. The Smith–Morland flow law (1) can then be rewritten as

$$\frac{d_{ij}}{[d]} = \tilde{A}(\tilde{T}) \left[c_0 + c_1 \left(\frac{\tau_e}{[\tau]} \right)^2 + c_2 \left(\frac{\tau_e}{[\tau]} \right)^4 \right] \frac{t_{ij}^{\text{D}}}{[\tau]}, \quad (6)$$

with the rescaled coefficients

$$c_0 = \frac{\beta}{\alpha} c_{0,\text{SM}}, \quad c_1 = \frac{\beta}{\alpha^3} c_{1,\text{SM}}, \quad c_2 = \frac{\beta}{\alpha^5} c_{2,\text{SM}}. \quad (7)$$

In the above-mentioned follow-up studies, $\alpha = 5$ and $\beta = 200$ were used, which corresponds to the scales $[\tau] = 10^5$ Pa, $[d] = 1 \text{ a}^{-1}$, and produces the flow-law coefficients $c_0 = 0.3336$, $c_1 = 0.3200$, $c_2 = 0.02963$. However, while the scale for the deviatoric stress is reasonable, the scale for the strain rate is still unrealistically large, so that non-dimensionalized strain rates will not be of order unity. Therefore, here

we choose

$$\alpha = 5, \quad \beta = 8000, \quad (8)$$

to produce the scales that were introduced by Greve (2025),

$$[\tau] = 10^5 \text{ Pa} \quad (\text{typical deviatoric stress}), \quad (9a)$$

$$[d] = 2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1} \quad (\text{typical strain rate}). \quad (9b)$$

By using Eq. (7), this yields the rescaled coefficients for the flow law (6)

$$c_0 = 13.34, \quad c_1 = 12.80, \quad c_2 = 1.185. \quad (10)$$

In the non-dimensional framework by Greve (2025), the rate factor recommended by Cuffey and Paterson (2010) (Arrhenius law with two sets of parameters for $T' \leq -10^\circ\text{C}$ and $T' \geq -10^\circ\text{C}$, respectively) has the value $\tilde{A} = 1$ for $T' = -5.8457^\circ\text{C}$. To achieve better comparability with the Smith–Morland rate factor (4), we multiply the latter by the factor 5.9821, so that it also takes the value $\tilde{A}(T' = -5.8457^\circ\text{C}) = 1$. The rate factor then becomes

$$\tilde{A}(\tilde{T}) = 4.3322 \exp(11.9567 \tilde{T}) + 2.0566 \exp(2.9494 \tilde{T}), \quad \tilde{T} = \frac{T' - T_0}{[\Delta T]}. \quad (11)$$

It is shown in Figure 1 together with the dimensionless rate factor by Cuffey and Paterson (2010). To compensate, the flow-law coefficients of Eq. (10) must be divided by the same factor 5.9821, resulting in

$$c_0 = 2.231, \quad c_1 = 2.140, \quad c_2 = 0.1981. \quad (12)$$

Following Greve (2025), we introduce the dimensionless quantities

$$t_{ij}^D = [\tau] \tilde{t}_{ij}^D, \quad (13a)$$

$$\tau_e = [\tau] \tilde{\tau}_e, \quad (13b)$$

$$d_{ij} = [d] \tilde{d}_{ij}, \quad (13c)$$

where the quantities marked by the tilde symbol are the non-dimensional components of the stress deviator,

Fig. 1. Dimensionless rate factor \tilde{A} as a function of the temperature relative to pressure melting T' by Cuffey and Paterson (2010) [dashed line labelled “CP10”; see also Greve (2025)] and by Smith and Morland (1981) [solid line labelled “SM81”], the latter rescaled such that both functions share the common value $\tilde{A} = 1$ for $T' = -5.8457^\circ\text{C}$ [Eq. (11)].

effective stress and components of the strain-rate tensor, respectively, and the scales are understood to be those of Eq. (9). We can then formulate the rescaled Smith–Morland flow law (6) in non-dimensional form,

$$\tilde{d}_{ij} = \tilde{A}(\tilde{T}) (c_0 + c_1 \tilde{\tau}_e^2 + c_2 \tilde{\tau}_e^4) \tilde{t}_{ij}^D. \quad (14)$$

68 It is still fully equivalent to the original Smith–Morland flow law (Sect. 2.1). However, it has the advantage
 69 that all dimensionless quantities will be generally of order unity for the high-temperature regime (i.e.,
 70 temperatures close to pressure melting, $T' \approx -15 \dots 0^\circ\text{C}$) that is most relevant for the dynamics of ice
 71 sheets and glaciers.

72 3 MODIFIED SMITH–MORLAND FLOW LAW

73 3.1 Flow enhancement factor

The Smith–Morland flow law is valid for the viscous flow (secondary creep) of pure, isotropic, polycrystalline ice. As usual in ice-sheet and glacier modelling (e.g., Greve and Blatter, 2009), softening due to the presence of impurities or an anisotropic fabric can be crudely accounted for by introducing a flow enhancement factor E ,

$$\tilde{A}(\tilde{T}) \rightarrow E\tilde{A}(\tilde{T}). \quad (15)$$

The Smith–Morland flow law (14) then becomes

$$\tilde{d}_{ij} = E\tilde{A}(\tilde{T}) \underbrace{(c_0 + c_1\tilde{\tau}_e^2 + c_2\tilde{\tau}_e^4)}_{\tilde{f}(\tilde{\tau}_e)} \tilde{t}_{ij}^D, \quad (16)$$

74 where we have introduced the dimensionless creep function $\tilde{f}(\tilde{\tau}_e)$ as an abbreviation for the three-term
75 polynomial.

76 3.2 Recalibration by idealized EISMINT tests

77 Suppose a typical shear-flow situation in the vertical x - z plane with $\tilde{t}_{xz}^D = 1$, $\tilde{\tau}_e = 1$, $\tilde{A} = 1$ and $E = 1$. The
78 strain rate resulting from Eq. (14) is then $\tilde{d}_{xz} = c_0 + c_1 + c_2 = 4.569$. By contrast, the dimensionless Nye–
79 Glen flow law by Greve (2025) (based on Glen (1955), Nye (1957) and Cuffey and Paterson (2010)) produces
80 $\tilde{d}_{xz} = 1$ for the same situation. Since the Nye–Glen flow law has been used in numerous applications to
81 real-world problems and has proved to provide realistic flow velocities, we consider the strain rate of the
82 Smith–Morland flow law to be too large.

83 To recalibrate the flow law, we have implemented it in the SICOPOLIS model (see Appendix A), and
84 first carry out experiment A of the EISMINT Phase 2 Simplified Geometry Experiments (Payne and others,
85 2000) in two variants:

86 Experiment A1:

87 Nye–Glen flow law with stress exponent $n = 3$ (original set-up),
88 rate factor by Cuffey and Paterson (2010) (Fig. 1, dashed line).

89 Experiment A2:

90 Original (rescaled) Smith–Morland flow law,
91 Smith–Morland rate factor (Fig. 1, solid line).

92 No-slip conditions are assumed at the ice base, which suits the purpose of this exercise well because we
93 aim at comparing flow laws, which govern internal deformation only. As a consequence, no ice-stream-like
94 flow dominated by basal sliding will occur, so that modelling ice dynamics by the shallow-ice approximation
95 (SIA) (Hutter, 1983; Morland, 1984) deems appropriate. For ice thermodynamics we employ the melting-
96 CTS enthalpy method (CTS: cold-temperate transition surface) (Greve and Blatter, 2016). The horizontal
97 resolution is 10 km, and we integrate over a model time of 200 ka, which is sufficient to reach a steady state

98 for the experiments. The flow enhancement factor is set to $E = 1$. For a list of physical parameters, see
 99 Table 2 by Payne and others (2000).

100 Results for the ice thickness and surface velocity are shown in Figure 2 (top and middle row). Ex-
 101 periment A1 produces a circularly symmetric ice sheet with a volume of $2.234 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^3$, a maximum
 102 ice thickness of 3837.4 m and a maximum surface velocity of 56.64 m a^{-1} . [These numbers are all means
 103 for the final 10 ka of the 200 ka model time.] As claimed above, the original Smith–Morland flow law is
 104 significantly faster than the standard Nye–Glen flow law: for experiment A2, the volume is $1.759 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^3$
 105 (21.3% smaller), the maximum thickness is 3128.2 m (18.5% thinner), and the maximum surface velocity
 106 is 78.55 m a^{-1} (38.7% faster).

107 To recalibrate the Smith–Morland flow law, we repeat experiment A2 with an additional slow-down
 108 factor (inverse flow enhancement factor) $S = 1/E$, targeting at reproducing the volume simulated by
 109 experiment A1. A scan for $S = 4, 5, 6, 7, 8$ (Fig. 3) shows that a value of S between 5 and 6 will be
 110 required. We then carry out three Newton iterations, starting with $S = 5$ and using the slope computed
 111 with the results from $S = 5$ and $S = 6$. This procedure yields a value of $S = 5.776$. Further iterations do
 112 not improve the convergence due to a slight noisiness of the simulated volumes.

Therefore, we absorb the slow-down factor $S = 5.776$ into the coefficients c_0, c_1, c_2 (Eq. (12)), which
 yields

$$c_0 = 0.3862, \quad c_1 = 0.3704, \quad c_2 = 0.03430. \quad (17)$$

113 The flow law (16) with the scales of Eq. (9), the rate factor (11) and the coefficients of Eq. (17) shall be
 114 referred to as the “modified Smith–Morland flow law”.

115 It is interesting to note that Morland (1984) already reported that the original flow law overpredicts
 116 observed strain rates for ice shelves, and suggested an enhancement factor $E = 0.2$ (equivalent to a slow-
 117 down factor $S = 5$) to improve the fit (his Eqs. (3.8) and (3.9)). This value is close to our slow-down factor
 118 $S = 5.776$.

119 We use the modified Smith–Morland flow law to define one more variant of the EISMINT tests:

120 Experiment A3:

121 Modified Smith–Morland flow law,

122 Smith–Morland rate factor (Fig. 1, solid line).

123 As a result of the iterations, the ice sheet simulated by experiment A3 (Fig. 2, bottom row) is very similar to

Fig. 2. Simulated ice thickness and surface velocity for the three experiments (A1, A2, A3) described in the main text (Sect. 3.2) after 200 ka model time.

Fig. 3. Simulated ice volume (mean for the final 10 ka model time) for experiment A2 (Smith–Morland flow law) with varied slow-down factor (inverse flow enhancement factor) S . The horizontal dashed line indicates the target volume from experiment A1 (Nye–Glen flow law), the vertical dashed line the slow-down factor $S = 5.776$ for which a good match (< 10 ppm difference) is achieved (experiment A3).

124 the one from experiment A1, with an essentially identical volume (< 10 ppm difference, marked in Fig. 3),
 125 a maximum thickness of 3915.9 m (2.05% thicker) and a maximum surface velocity of 56.59 m a^{-1} (0.101%
 126 slower). This demonstrates that our construction of the modified Smith–Morland flow law is successful in
 127 producing strain rates comparable to those of the standard Nye–Glen flow law.

128 It is interesting to note that the flow fields of experiments A2 and A3 (with the Smith–Morland flow law)
 129 show a fingering instability that results from the thermomechanical coupling. By contrast, the instability
 130 does not occur in experiment A1 (Nye–Glen flow law), where the solution for the flow field maintains an
 131 almost perfect circular symmetry. This instability was already discussed in the original EISMINT paper
 132 (Payne and others, 2000) and in further studies (Fowler and Johnson, 1996; Payne and Dongelmans, 1997;
 133 Sayag and Tziperman, 2008; Hindmarsh, 2009). Greve (2025) carried out tests with the Nye–Glen flow
 134 law for the EISMINT experiment H, which differs from our experiment A by including basal sliding in the
 135 Weertman–Budd form $v_b \propto \tau_b^p / N_b^q$, where v_b is the basal sliding velocity, τ_b the basal shear stress and N_b
 136 the basal normal stress. In these tests, the instability appeared for the sliding exponents $(p, q) = (1, 0)$,
 137 but not for $(p, q) = (3, 2)$. The former parameters allow more basal sliding in the interior of the ice sheet,
 138 while the latter concentrate sliding near the margin. Similarly, in our tests, the Smith–Morland flow law
 139 produces relatively more ice flow in the interior and relatively less near the margin because of the presence
 140 of the linear term. So, it seems that any conditions that favour ice flow (either due to internal deformation
 141 or basal sliding) in interior regions where the driving stress is rather small also favour the occurrence of

142 the fingering instability.

143 4 INVERSION OF THE MODIFIED SMITH–MORLAND FLOW LAW

For any ice dynamics formulations that go beyond SIA, the modified Smith–Morland flow law is required in its inverted form (that is, solved for the stresses \tilde{t}_{ij}^D). To obtain this stress formulation, we introduce the effective strain rate $d_e = [(d_{ij}d_{ij})/2]^{1/2}$. For its non-dimensionalization, we use the scale $[d]$ of Eq. (9), so that

$$d_e = [d] \tilde{d}_e. \quad (18)$$

The inverted flow law in dimensionless form must be in the general form of a viscous flow law,

$$\tilde{t}_{ij}^D = 2\tilde{\eta}(\tilde{T}, \tilde{d}_e) \tilde{d}_{ij}, \quad (19)$$

where $\tilde{\eta}$ is the dimensionless viscosity, depending on the temperature relative to pressure melting and the effective strain rate. Its dimensional counterpart η is given by

$$\eta = \frac{[\tau]}{[d]} \tilde{\eta}, \quad (20)$$

144 with the scale $[\tau]/[d] = (10^5/0.025) \text{ Pa a} = 1.262 \times 10^{14} \text{ Pa s}$.

In contrast to the Nye–Glen flow law, an exact analytical inversion of the modified Smith–Morland flow law is not possible. An approximate analytical formulation can be achieved (e.g., Morland and Staroszczyk, 2003, Sect. 2.2); however, here we derive an implicit expression for the viscosity. The tensorial equations (16) and (19) hold also for the effective stresses and strain rates:

$$\tilde{d}_e = E\tilde{A} \tilde{f}(\tilde{\tau}_e) \tilde{\tau}_e, \quad (21)$$

$$\tilde{\tau}_e = 2\tilde{\eta} \tilde{d}_e. \quad (22)$$

By inserting Eq. (22) in (21), we can eliminate the effective stress:

$$\tilde{d}_e = E\tilde{A} \tilde{f}(2\tilde{\eta}\tilde{d}_e) 2\tilde{\eta} \tilde{d}_e. \quad (23)$$

Provided that $\tilde{d}_e > 0$, this can be readily rearranged as

$$2\tilde{\eta} E \tilde{A} \tilde{f}(2\tilde{\eta}\tilde{d}_e) - 1 = 0, \quad (24)$$

145 which is an implicit equation for the viscosity $\tilde{\eta}(\tilde{T}, \tilde{d}_e)$ of the inverted flow law (19) that can be solved
 146 numerically for any given pair of values (\tilde{T}, \tilde{d}_e) using a suitable root-finding algorithm. See Appendix A
 147 for the concrete implementation in SICOPOLIS.

148 5 TEST SIMULATIONS FOR THE GREENLAND ICE SHEET

149 To test the behaviour of the Smith–Morland flow law also for a real-world application, we consider a
 150 present-day steady-state spin-up scenario for the Greenland ice sheet, and define three experiments similar
 151 to Sect. 3.2:

152 Experiment Gr1:

153 Nye–Glen flow law with stress exponent $n = 3$,
 154 rate factor by Cuffey and Paterson (2010) (Fig. 1, dashed line).

155 Experiment Gr2:

156 Original (rescaled) Smith–Morland flow law,
 157 Smith–Morland rate factor (Fig. 1, solid line).

158 Experiment Gr3:

159 Modified Smith–Morland flow law,
 160 Smith–Morland rate factor (Fig. 1, solid line).

161 The simulations run over 100 ka to reach steady-state conditions. An important difference from the
 162 EISMINT simulations discussed above (Sect. 3.2) is that, rather than allowing the ice topography to evolve
 163 freely, we employ a topography-nudging scheme that keeps the simulated topography always close to the
 164 present-day observed one (with some leeway). See Appendix B for a detailed description of the set-up.

165 Due to the topography-nudging scheme (which is equivalent to a systematic correction of the surface
 166 mass balance), the simulated topography of the ice sheet agrees very well with the observed one (not shown).
 167 Results for the surface velocity are depicted in Figure 4a-c. As expected, they are similar to one another
 168 for experiments Gr1 and Gr3, whereas experiment Gr2 produces distinctly faster ice flow. Comparison

Fig. 4. (a–c) Simulated surface velocity for the three experiments (Gr1, Gr2, Gr3) described in the main text (Sect. 5) after 100 ka model time. (d) Observed surface velocity (Joughin and others, 2016, 2018). (e) Scatter plot of the simulated surface velocities of exp. Gr3 (modified Smith–Morland flow law) vs. exp. Gr1 (Nye–Glen flow law).

169 with observations (Fig. 4d) reveals that the surface velocities from experiments Gr1 and Gr3 are realistic,
170 while those from Gr2 are clearly too large. This finding supports our previous claim (Sect. 3.2) that the
171 original (rescaled) Smith–Morland flow law overpredicts strain rates and thus flow velocities. However, due
172 to the rather simplistic set-up of the experiments (steady state, limited resolution, ad-hoc choice of the
173 sliding coefficient), we refrain from a more detailed comparison between simulated and observed surface
174 velocities.

175 Differences between the surface velocities simulated by experiment Gr3 (modified Smith–Morland) vs.
176 Gr1 (Nye–Glen) are shown as a scatter plot in Figure 4e. The velocities are very similar in areas with
177 rather fast flow ($\gtrsim 50 \text{ m a}^{-1}$), while in the slower-flow regime Gr3 tends to feature larger velocities than
178 Gr1. This is explicable by the presence of the linear term in the modified Smith–Morland flow law, which
179 leads to relatively more ice flow in areas with smaller stress. We do not attempt to judge which of the
180 results from the two experiments is more realistic.

181 6 SUMMARY

182 We have reconsidered the polynomial Smith–Morland flow law as an alternative to the widely used Nye–
183 Glen flow law. While the Nye–Glen law is a standard in glaciology, it suffers from a physically doubtful
184 infinite-viscosity singularity at zero stress. In contrast, the Smith–Morland law utilizes a three-term poly-
185 nomial that includes a linear term, naturally preventing this singularity.

186 In this study, we first rescaled the Smith–Morland flow law to align with a modern non-dimensional
187 framework. We demonstrated that the original parameters result in ice that is significantly too “soft”,
188 leading to unrealistically high flow velocities. To address this, we recalibrated the law using an idealized
189 EISMINT Phase 2 test, iteratively adjusting the coefficients until the steady-state ice volume matched
190 results obtained with the standard Nye–Glen law. This resulted in a “modified Smith–Morland flow law”
191 with a slow-down factor of $S = 5.776$.

192 The modified law was further validated through a steady-state simulation of the Greenland ice sheet.
193 Our results show that while the modified Smith–Morland and Nye–Glen laws produce broadly similar
194 surface velocities, the Smith–Morland law predicts slightly faster flow in low-stress regions due to its linear
195 term. Furthermore, the Smith–Morland law appears to favour thermomechanical fingering instabilities in
196 the interior of ice sheets, which are suppressed by the Nye–Glen law. These findings suggest that the
197 modified Smith–Morland flow law is a viable, singularity-free alternative for large-scale ice-sheet modelling

198 that may capture physical instabilities in slow-moving ice.

199 **OPEN SCIENCE**

200 SICOPOLIS (SICOPOLIS Authors, 2025) is free and open-source software, published in a persistent Git
201 repository hosted by GitHub (<https://github.com/sicopolis/sicopolis/>). The run-specs headers and output
202 data produced for this study are available at Zenodo, [LINK] (not yet available, we will provide the data
203 at a later stage).

204 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

205 Both authors conceptualized the study. Ralf Greve developed the modified flow law with contributions
206 from Ryszard Staroszczyk. Ralf Greve ran the SICOPOLIS simulations and created the figures. Both
207 authors discussed and interpreted the results. Ralf Greve wrote the manuscript with contributions from
208 Ryszard Staroszczyk.

209 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

210 We are deeply grateful to Leslie W. Morland (University of East Anglia, Norwich, UK) for a fruitful,
211 long-term collaboration regarding the development of flow laws for polycrystalline ice.

212 **COMPETING INTERESTS**

213 Ralf Greve serves as an Associate Chief Editor of the *Journal of Glaciology*.

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324 APPENDIX

325 A IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SMITH–MORLAND FLOW LAW IN SICOPOLIS

Since SICOPOLIS is formulated with dimensional quantities, we implement the dimensional counterpart of the flow law (16),

$$d_{ij} = E\tilde{A}(\tilde{T}) \underbrace{(k_0 + k_1\tau_e^2 + k_2\tau_e^4)}_{f(\tau_e)} t_{ij}^D, \quad (25)$$

where the coefficients $k_{\{0,1,2\}}$ are the dimensional counterparts of $c_{\{0,1,2\}}$,

$$k_0 = \frac{[d]}{[\tau]} c_0, \quad k_1 = \frac{[d]}{[\tau]^3} c_1, \quad k_2 = \frac{[d]}{[\tau]^5} c_2. \quad (26)$$

326 Note that the rate factor $\tilde{A}(\tilde{T})$ remains dimensionless.

The dimensional form of the inverted flow law (19) reads

$$t_{ij}^D = 2\eta(T', d_e) d_{ij}, \quad (27)$$

where the viscosity is given by the dimensional form of Eq. (24),

$$g(\eta) := 2\eta E\tilde{A} f(2\eta d_e) - 1 = 2\eta E\tilde{A} (k_0 + 4k_1 d_e^2 \eta^2 + 16k_2 d_e^4 \eta^4) - 1 = 0. \quad (28)$$

To solve this implicit equation, we start with an initial guess of $\eta = 10^{10}$ Pa s, which is safely less than any realistic values to be expected. Therefore, the function $g(\eta)$ will be negative. We then increase η repeatedly by a factor 10 until $g(\eta)$ becomes positive. This order-of-magnitude estimate serves as the starting value η_0 for Newton's method,

$$\eta_{k+1} = \eta_k - \frac{g(\eta_k)}{g'(\eta_k)} \quad (k = 0, 1, 2, \dots), \quad (29)$$

where the derivative $g'(\eta)$ is

$$g'(\eta) = 2E\tilde{A} (k_0 + 12k_1 d_e^2 \eta^2 + 80k_2 d_e^4 \eta^4). \quad (30)$$

327 The iterations are continued until the residual value of $g(\eta)$ is less than 10^{-5} .

328 The implementation of the modified Smith–Morland flow law as described above is available since
329 SICOPOLIS v25 (SICOPOLIS Authors, 2025), revision 35038c47c of 14 August 2025.

330 B SET-UP OF THE SIMULATIONS FOR THE GREENLAND ICE SHEET

331 The model time of the three steady-state test simulations for the Greenland ice sheet is 100 ka. The domain
332 covers the entire area of Greenland and the surrounding oceans. We use the EPSG:3413 grid, based on
333 a polar stereographic projection with the WGS 84 reference ellipsoid, standard parallel 70°N and central
334 meridian 45°W. The stereographic plane, spanned by the Cartesian coordinates x and y , is discretized by a
335 regular (structured) grid with 16 km resolution. In the vertical, we use terrain-following coordinates (sigma
336 transformation) with 81 layers in the ice domain and 41 layers in the thermal lithosphere layer below. The
337 dynamics of grounded ice is modelled by a hybrid SIA–SSa formulation (SIA: shallow-ice approximation,
338 SSa: shelfy-stream approximation) (Bernales and others, 2017; Greve and others, 2020a). Floating ice
339 is ignored. Ice thermodynamics is modelled by the melting-CTS enthalpy method (CTS: cold-temperate

340 transition surface) (Greve and Blatter, 2016). The flow enhancement factor is chosen as $E = 2.5$ for slow-
341 flowing grounded ice older than 11 ka (glacial ice), $E = 1$ for slow-flowing grounded ice younger than 11 ka
342 (interglacial ice) and $E = 1$ for ice streams.

343 The ice surface is assumed to be traction-free. Basal sliding is described by a Weertman–Budd sliding
344 law accounting for sub-melt sliding and the subglacial water-layer thickness (Greve and others, 2020b,
345 Eqs. (1), (2) and accompanying text). For the sliding coefficient, we use values of $C_b^0 = 0.5 \text{ m a}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ for
346 all regions except for the north-east Greenland ice stream (NEGIS) and $C_b^0 = 5 \text{ m a}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ for the NEGIS
347 (based on the previous finding that the NEGIS requires substantially more basal sliding; e.g., Greve and
348 others, 2020b, Sect. 3.2). In the dimensionless framework by Greve (2025), these values are equivalent
349 to $\tilde{C}_b^0 = 0.05$ and 0.5 , respectively. In contrast to Greve and others (2020b), we use a sub-melt-sliding
350 parameter $\gamma = \infty$ here, so that basal sliding can in principle occur everywhere, irrespective of the basal
351 temperature. However, the dependence on the thickness of the subglacial water layer strongly favours
352 sliding for a temperate base. Since the objective of our simulations is merely to test the flow laws, we
353 refrain from a regional tuning of the basal sliding coefficient beyond the choice of a separate, larger value
354 for the NEGIS.

355 For the present-day mean annual and mean-July surface temperature, we employ the parameterizations
356 by Fausto and others (2009) with an offset of -1°C (Greve and others, 2020b). For the present-day pre-
357 cipitation, we use monthly means for the period 1958–2001, created with the regional energy and moisture
358 balance model REMBO (Robinson and others, 2010). Surface melting is parameterized by Reeh’s (1991)
359 positive degree day (PDD) method, supplemented by the semi-analytical solution for the PDD integral by
360 Calov and Greve (2005). The PDD factors are $\beta_{\text{ice}} = 8 \text{ mm WE d}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ and $\beta_{\text{snow}} = 3 \text{ mm WE d}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
361 for ice and snow melt, respectively (where WE means water equivalent) (Huybrechts and de Wolde, 1999).
362 Furthermore, the standard deviation of short-term, statistical air temperature fluctuations is $\sigma = 5^\circ\text{C}$, and
363 the saturation factor for the formation of superimposed ice is chosen as $P_{\text{max}} = 0.6$ (Reeh, 1991). The
364 bed topography is BedMachine v5 (Morlighem and others, 2017; Morlighem and others, 2022). Glacial
365 isostatic adjustment (GIA) is included using an elastic-lithosphere–relaxing-asthenosphere (ELRA) model
366 (Le Meur and Huybrechts, 1996). The geothermal heat flux is by Greve (2019).

367 To ensure a good match, the computed ice thickness and bed topography are continuously nudged
368 towards their (slightly smoothed) observed present-day counterparts. This is done by the method described
369 by Rückamp and others (2019) with a constant relaxation time $\tau = 100 \text{ a}$.